

Appendix 1.

Table A1. Standardized coefficients of the factors analysed in the linear regression. Full model including all variables.

Factors	Value	Standard error	t	Pr > t	Lower limit (95%)	Upper limit (95%)
Social importance of agricultural landscapes	0.366	0.100	3.667	0.001	0.167	0.566
Importance of Provisioning ecosystem services	0.000	0.000				
Importance of Regulating ecosystem services	-0.183	0.102	-1.799	0.077	-0.387	0.020
Importance of Cultural ecosystem services	0.168	0.108	1.562	0.123	-0.047	0.384
Average of the importance of the ecosystem services	0.000	0.000				
Satisfaction with life	0.000	0.000				
Perceived social support	0.000	0.000				
Time spent regularly outdoors	0.346	0.099	3.506	0.001	0.149	0.543
Time spent entertainment outdoors	0.000	0.000				
Linkages with agricultural activities	0.210	0.102	2.066	0.043	0.007	0.413
Studies	0.000	0.000				
Age	0.000	0.000				
Female gender	0.310	0.103	3.016	0.004	0.105	0.516
Land owner	0.000	0.000				
Rural residence	-0.160	0.098	-1.621	0.110	-0.356	0.037